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ENLIGHT RISE- RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA WITH AND FOR SOCIETY: LEVERAGING DIGITAL INNOVATION FOR A GREENER AND HEALTHIER EUROPE

WP No	Del. Rel. No	Del No	Title	Lead beneficiary
WP6	D6.3	D32	<i>Final report on experiences, learning and recommendations for engagement activities with civic society</i>	RUG

Nature	Dissemination Level	Related to Del. No (if applicable)
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Description (short)		
<i>This describes our experience in fostering Public Engagement across the ENLIGHT Alliance; we describe what we learned and give recommendations for those also interested in fostering Public Engagement.</i>		

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Introduction

This report compiles experiences in fostering Public Engagement (PE) across all ENLIGHT partner universities. The information in this document was gathered through a survey distributed among ENLIGHT-RISE partner universities in May 2024. It outlines our collective ENLIGHT approach and experience in fostering PE and shares the lessons learned during this process. Additionally, we have collected recommendations for other university alliances that are also striving to promote PE.

After obtaining agreement from the partners, we have decided to include an Appendix consisting of ENLIGHT PE experience stories collected for deliverable D6.2, *Action plan to sustain ENLIGHT engagement activities with civil society in Research, Innovation, Learning and Teaching*. The information in D6.2 covered a wide range of experiences, learning, and recommendations, but was previously treated as confidential and only accessible to the European Commission and the Consortium Members.

Starting from September 2021, after conducting an extensive mapping exercise to identify current PE structures and activities across the ENLIGHT consortium, a network of PE professionals within ENLIGHT has been formed, with 89 individuals currently involved. Our approach to promoting PE involved not only building a network of experts and enthusiasts, but also offering a series of workshops and webinars to strengthen our community of practice and provide diverse opportunities for mutual learning.

With thanks to all involved in WP6 at the ENLIGHT partners,

Henk Mulder
WP-Leader, University of Groningen
July 2024.

The Public Engagement Work Package of ENLIGHT-RISE

This chapter describes our activities and indicates what worked well and what was and is challenging. It is based on a survey among the experts of the nine RISE partners that were associated to this work package, and an online meeting with them.

The mission of the ENLIGHT Alliance states:

ENLIGHT aims to conduct an impact-driven and challenge-based transformation of European higher education to empower learners as globally engaged citizens with state-of-the-art knowledge and skills, while synergizing our R&I potential with and for our societal partners, to tackle major societal transitions and promote equitable quality of life and sustainability.

To achieve challenge-based research and teaching collaboration with and for societal partners, expertise in public engagement, engaged teaching, and co-production of knowledge is indispensable. In ENLIGHT-RISE, WP6, the expertise of the Alliance members in PE and co-creation was mapped, which helped us build a varied Community of Practice for PE-professionals across the Alliance.

This WP aimed to *foster genuine engagement of civil society actors (citizens, civil society organizations, communities, municipalities, non-profits/3rd sector) in ENLIGHT research and innovation activities (from setting research agendas to executing the research, analyzing and interpreting findings and discussing follow-up and creating impact), thus co-creating knowledge, as well as including students in this collaboration.*

This meant an endeavour to support each partner to climb up the so-called 'Ladder of Engagement', i.e. moving from sending information towards dialogue, involvement of civil society actors in research, and ultimately co-creation of knowledge.

Activities

We started by making an [inventory](#) of current activities and structures for PE across the ENLIGHT partner universities. In our initial mapping exercise, we gained a comprehensive understanding of PE activities, and structures, and got to know PE experts across ENLIGHT. As a result, we organized three networking webinars for experts in different PE fields such as service learning, science shops, university museums, and multidisciplinary schools. The purpose of these webinars was to establish connections between PE experts within the alliance and initiate discussions before WP6 finalized the topics for mutual learning webinars. Additionally, the networking webinar enabled us to set up a Community of Practice, which

now comprises over 80 specialists and enthusiasts in the field of public engagement. All are subscribed and active on the Community-of-Practice [mailing list](#).

To further advance mutual learning, the WP6-Team organized eight publicly available [webinars](#) on various topics:

Title	Speaker(s)	University
Science Shops	Dr. Henk Mulder	University of Groningen
Impact of Science Communication	Dr. Anne Land	Leiden University (External)
Service Learning	Dr. Lorraine Tansey	University of Galway
Citizen Science	Dr. Mohammad Gharesifard and Niels Alberts, MSc.	University of Groningen
Impact in Academia	Dr. Igor Campillo and Gloria Nunes Rodrigues, MA	University of the Basque Country
The set-up of a workshop on social media use for researchers	Larissa van der Wal, MSc	University of Groningen
Engaging with the cultural sector	Yorick Karseboom, MA and Vincent Hazelhoff, MA	University of Groningen
Social Justice at the centre of learning & teaching in Law	Dr. Alazne Irigoyen	University of the Basque Country

Additionally, we have organized five on-site workshops (offered by University of Groningen) at partner universities in Bilbao, Bratislava, Bordeaux, Groningen, and Tartu. In organizing these workshops, our aim was to bring together the community of practice within different universities, to strengthen the institutional network of PE experts, and to discuss best practices at University of Groningen and different institutes at the hosting university. This also led to an exchange among representatives of various departments and stakeholders of the host university (who may not have been in contact with each other previously).

In general, thanks to the WP6 ENLIGHT RISE, the ENLIGHT partners have created an overview of all PE-activities within their institution and have started to build and strengthen a Community of Practice at the institutional level.

Thanks to many discussions we can see a strive to intensify connections between academia and external organizations/partners and the public in the regional surroundings. Some partners are also taking steps towards co-production of knowledge, i.e. research and

challenge-based teaching both *with* and *for* society. Citizen Science seems to become an important approach for many partners.

The experience and learning according to partners

Positive Experiences

- **Mapping:** For some partners, mapping PE activities was a novel and beneficial exercise, providing a clearer understanding of ongoing projects and facilitating better support.
- **Knowledge Exchange:** There has been a significant exchange of ideas and learning among universities. The webinars were instrumental in this. The dedicated PE website with an overview of activities is an important asset.
- **Workshops:** In-person workshops have been instrumental in laying the groundwork for future collaboration and increasing awareness of PE activities at universities.
- **Relevance:** The relevance and importance of activities related to Public Engagement for ENLIGHT's desired Impact became clear.

Challenges

- **Reach:** Reaching a broad audience for webinars has been challenging; on average 20 people actively participate (and up to 70 views of the respective videos). There are still some topic suggestions from partners, but in practice it is difficult to get spontaneous offers from partners to speak at or moderate a webinar.
- **Collaboration:** It remains difficult to get sub-communities to work together on joint projects.
- **Central Mapping:** it is difficult to keep the overview of structures and activities for PE at partners up to date.
- **Resource Allocation:** Some partners have difficulties to map all PE-activities. Despite numerous PE activities, dedicated resources for supporting these initiatives remain insufficient. This hampers 'stepping up the Ladder of Engagement'.
- **Local PE networks:** For some partners, engaging individuals from their universities in PE activities and broadening their perspective on PE has been difficult.
- **Project based work:** Collaboration between ENLIGHT RISE, ENLIGHT and ENLIGHT 2.0 (i.e. both Erasmus funded projects and the H2020 funded RISE project) and even across WPs within RISE has been difficult (time pressure, strict schedules, and deliverables).

Recommendations to the ENLIGHT alliance regarding Public Engagement

- **Broader Perspective:** The Alliance should not only focus on project objectives but also consider the broader needs of all universities, with PE at the forefront. An international exchange on PE is found to be important considering international (political) developments and the importance of involving society in research and education developments.
- **Collaboration of PE-experts with Impact-experts:** Try to avoid working in silos. Public engagement can go hand-in-hand with creating impact.
- **Leveraging Geographical Diversity:** Utilize the diverse geographical locations of the partners to develop and test common methods for supporting PE initiatives with an international perspective, linked to ENLIGHT Expert-Networks.
- **Incentives and Funding:** More resources for dedicated people to work at an institutional level to engage with civil society actors.
- **Recognize** the importance of PE activities by including them in evaluation criteria for inter-alliance calls and preparing special calls exclusively for PE activities.

In conclusion, to foster the interactivity of public engagement, and move up on the “Ladder of Participation”, we propose to the ENLIGHT alliance to continue and strengthen the CoP-PE within ENLIGHT, to support, recognize and reward challenge-based education and research with and for society. This can be done by recognizing PE activities during internal calls or awards, exchanging good practices, keeping our online overview of PE structures and activities up to date, maintaining the mailing list of PE-professionals, and continuing to organize webinars, train-the-trainer workshops, etc. This way, partners can stimulate interactive engagement and collective research/teaching projects, and teachers and researchers can be equipped with the necessary skills, and students are prepared to become global citizens.

Recommendations to other University Alliances that want to advance Public Engagement

Mapping: Our mapping survey led to rich results, but the initial questionnaire was too complicated (including asking for the ‘levels of engagement’). It is better to do this ordering ex-post by PE experts. Allocate time to keep the database of structures and activities up-to-date and searchable.

Recognize and Reward PE: Develop a strong vision of PE and impact, recognize and reward PE activities, and support PE facilitators across all partners.

Transparency and Motivation: Be open about needs and possibilities and find a highly motivated team to lead PE efforts.

Sharing Best Practices: Share effective strategies for involving audiences and facilitating PE activities; facilitate training courses in how to engage the public in research.

Embrace Online and In-Person Engagement: Combine online seminars with in-person connections.

Move Beyond Project-Based Activities: Transition from project-based activities to a sustained alliance, facilitating ongoing mutual learning and training on public engagement, and work towards better support from national and European funders.

Conclusion

The ENLIGHT-RISE project has made significant strides in enhancing public engagement across its partner institutions. Key achievements include the creation of a comprehensive PE activity map, the establishment of a Community of Practice (both among the partners and internally within the partner institute), and the development of knowledge exchange mechanisms (webinars, workshops).

However, challenges such as resource allocation, internal engagement, and sustaining collaboration across project-based activities remain, and hamper stepping up the Ladder of Public Engagement.

By implementing the recommendations outlined above, the ENLIGHT Alliance and other university alliances can further advance public engagement, ensuring that higher education institutions remain responsive to societal needs and continue to foster challenge-based learning and collaborative, impactful R&I.

Appendices

In these appendices, the experiences in our work package at the partner institutions are described.

These stories are part of another WP6 deliverable: D6.2 *Action plan to sustain ENLIGHT engagement activities with civil society in Research, Innovation, Learning, and Teaching*, which was a confidential deliverable for the European Commission and the Consortium Members.

We decided to add them as an appendix here because the stories of the partners in D6.2 contain such a wealth of information about their experiences that it would be both useful and highly beneficial to share them more broadly and that the public has a substantial amount to gain from including this information in this public report.

Therefore, we asked all partners if we could make their stories public, with some editing if needed. We received permission from all partners to publish the stories in their original form, with editing only typos, so we can now share these with you.

University of the Basque Country, Bilbao

BEFORE RISE

Before RISE, there were already some structures and activities, but they were done on their own 'islands'. In our first attempt to map PE activities at the University of the Basque Country, we identified the following items, already included in WP6's first deliverable:

PE TYPE	NAME OF ACTIVITY	WEB
MUSEUMS AND SCIENCE CENTERS	Basque Museum of the History of Medicine and Science	www.ehu.eus/en/web/basque-museum-medicine/home
MUSEUMS AND SCIENCE CENTERS	Museum of Education	https://www.ehu.eus/es/web/gipuzkoa/hezkuntzaren-museoa
SCIENCE SHOPS	Gaztenpatia	www.ehu.eus/en/web/oficop/gaztenpatia
UNITS ORGANIZING PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT	Chair of Scientific Culture of the UPV/EHU and Euskampus Fundazioa	https://katedra.eus/es/
UNITS ORGANIZING PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT	EHUgune	https://www.ehu.eus/es/web/ehugune/hasierako-orria
ORGANISATIONS SUPPORTING FORMAL AND INFORMAL EDUCATION	Senior Academy Bizkaia	https://www.ehu.eus/es/web/esperientzia-gelak-bizkaia
ORGANISATIONS SUPPORTING FORMAL AND INFORMAL EDUCATION	Senior Academy Gipuzkoa	https://www.ehu.eus/es/web/gipuzkoako-esperientzia-gelak
ORGANISATIONS SUPPORTING FORMAL AND INFORMAL EDUCATION	Senior Academy Araba	https://www.ehu.eus/es/web/esperientzia-gelak-araba

ONLINE INFORMATION SERVICES	Mapping Ignorance	mappingignorance.org
ONLINE INFORMATION SERVICES	Mujeres con Ciencia	mujeresconciencia.com
ONLINE INFORMATION SERVICES	Cuaderno de Cultura Científica	culturacientifica.com
ONLINE INFORMATION SERVICES	Zientzia Kaiera	zientziakaiera.eus
SCIENCE FESTIVALS AND EXHIBITIONS	European Researchers' Night	www.ikertzaileengaua-ehu.org/hasiera/
SCIENCE FESTIVALS AND EXHIBITIONS	Zientzia Astea (Science Week)	zientzia-astea.org/es/
HECKATHON	Ciencia Clip - Video Contest	cienciaclip.naukas.com
CITIZEN SCIENCE	Ocean i3: BLUE SKILLS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE BLUE ECONOMY IN THE BASQUE-AQUITAINE CROSS-BORDER COASTLINE	ocean3.com/en/inicio-english/
Co-Creation ALIANCE/LIVING LABS etc.	Campus Bizia Lab	https://www.ehu.eus/es/web/iraunkortasuna/campus-bizia-lab

DURING RISE

The visit of Henk Mulder to our institution in March 2023 to share his knowledge and further support the development of public engagement at the University of the Basque Country was a milestone for us, because it helped us understanding the importance of having a proper institutional structure for PE activities. Consequently, in September 2023, the Vice-rectorate for Scientific and Social Development and Transfer was restructured and it was created a new Office for Public Engagement and Social Impact (see <https://www.ehu.eus/es/web/gardentasun-ataria/ehugune-zuzendaritza-konpromisoa-eta-eragin-soziala>).

RISE also offered us time to map and better connect our internal activities. As a consequence, we have identified some activities not included in the previous mapping and some new PE activities, as shown in the next table:

PE TYPE	NAME OF ACTIVITY	WEB
CONSULTANCY SERVICES	Dental Clinic	https://www.ehu.eus/es/web/clinica.odontologica
CONSULTANCY SERVICES	Legal Clinic for Social Justice	https://www.ehu.eus/es/web/zuzenbide-fakultatea/gzkj
SERVICE LEARNING	Service Learning Lab	https://www.ehu.eus/es/web/sae-helaz
SERVICE LEARNING	Service Learning Room	https://www.ehu.eus/es/web/sae-helaz
HECKATHON	Impact of climate change on health	https://www.ehu.eus/es/web/iraunkortasuna/hackathon-sobre-crisis-climatica-y-salud
SCIENCE FESTIVALS AND EXHIBITIONS	Invisible Express Film Festival	https://www.ehu.eus/es/web/oficop/invisibleexpress
SCIENCE FESTIVALS AND EXHIBITIONS	Homeless Film Festival	https://homelessfestival.org/

Both the Invisible Express Film Festival and Homeless Film Festival have been running for the last 8-10 years. Their purpose is to engage students into social problems in their community by creating short movies. Students are in charge of deciding the topic as well as all the creative features.

The Dental Clinic of the University of the Basque Country is a teaching-care service to the community, in which the Dentistry students of the UPV/EHU carry out the corresponding clinical practices under the supervision of the teaching staff.

The Legal Clinic for Social Justice of the University of the Basque Country guides students to advice or involvement in cases and problems that have to do with social justice. The clinic aims at, on the one hand, transforming the pedagogical system of Law and, at the other, serving as a laboratory for reflection and identification of anti-discriminatory legal strategies through which students create awareness of their role in achieving a more just society.

The medical-humanitarian organization Medicos Sin Fronteras (MSF) organizes a Hackathon to effectively raise awareness about the impact of the climate crisis on people's health in collaboration with the University of the Basque Country.

Finally, the Service Learning Lab has been created in 2023 in order to better manage students interested in focus their final degree projects into solving problems of the community. The service is coordinated by the educational advisory service (SAE). Connected to the Lab, a Service Learning Room has also been created. The Room aims at matching students interested in service learning final degree projects with social needs provided by BizkaiaGara. BizkaiaGara is the space for citizen action, volunteering and community work at the service of people, institutions and organizations in the Basque province of Bizkaia, with the objective of reinforcing their voluntary commitment, generate new opportunities and contribute to extending social transformation at all levels and areas of action.

FUTURE

First of all, it is important to stress that we still face some limitations to what we can do in the near future because we are still on the way up the ladder of participation and because our institution is quite horizontal in its functioning meaning, on the one hand, that researchers and academics are free to engage in PE activities, but, on the other hand, that we sometimes have problems mapping and connecting these activities.

From the institutional perspective, we have continued strengthening public engagement at the University of the Basque Country creating a new position for an impact officer in the Office for Public Engagement and Social Impact from September 2023.

Also, an inclusive citizen science initiative has been launched in 2024 at the Plentzia Marine Station (PiE-UPV/EHU) called 'Attention! Don't crush me!'. This is a collaborative project that wants to promote knowledge about the Basque coast by focusing on biodiversity at a microscopic scale and the risks that endanger it, including plastics. The initiative, of a pedagogical nature, aims to make known the invisible (microscopic) world of the Basque sandy areas, in addition to influencing and raising awareness about the importance of care and conservation of the environment of the beaches and oceans. This activity will be also running in the following years.

Finally, we attempt to maintain all current PE activities in the future and, when possible, include new features that can help these activities to step up the ladder of engagement.

University of Bordeaux

The University of Bordeaux is one of twenty-one French universities to have been awarded the "Sciences with and for society" label by the Ministry of Higher Education and Research. The aim of this label is to "support innovative projects that promote the development of new interfaces for dialogue between science, research and society and the assertive structuring of a territorial network through partnerships with actors in the field of scientific mediation and communication, as well as with institutions and local authorities.

BEFORE RISE

The programme RISE coincided with the award of the "Science with and for Society" label, in recognition of the public engagement programme detailed in [the SUNSET \(Science with and for a Society in Transition\) project](#). Under this label, the University aims to:

1. Promote knowledge of the scientific method and its value in the production of knowledge, as widely and as closely as possible to the general public, with a view to inclusion and democratisation, in particular for those groups and regions that are furthest removed from the academic world.
2. Create the conditions for an open debate leading to informed choices at regional level on the major challenges of transition, through the joint experimentation of solutions and the sharing of scientific expertise.

Based on a better coordination of the many activities carried out within the University, these objectives are aimed at a large public on a wide regional scale, bringing together the actors of the CSTI (Scientific, Technical and Industrial Culture) and its partners. The SUNSET project is made up of 5 sections, each of which includes a programme of actions related to public engagement:

- Section 1. Citizen science, towards society transitions (living labs, science co-construction spaces and shared platform)
- Section 2. Working with schoolchildren and 2nd level education: stimulating interest in science (discovery of university courses, one class one researcher/one team programmes, summer schools).
- Section 3. Promotion of research, science and heritage (promotion of collections, etc.)
- Section 4. Democratisation of knowledge (new media, promotion of parity, combating social and territorial inequalities)

- Section 5. Training and education of human resources (outreach, citizen science)

Before RISE and before the SAPS/SWAFS label, many structures and activities were in place, and the result of an inventory invited us to structure this panel of public engagement actions.

DURING RISE

The first year of SAPS/SWAFS accreditation at University of Bordeaux (UB) from 2022 onwards was primarily devoted to identifying and structuring an extensive network of internal actors and partners. Emphasis was placed on the establishment of governance and real operational management, reflecting the institution's desire to make this policy a long-term one and to establish itself as a key player in the dialogue between science and society in the region. The momentum generated in 2022-23 has enabled the implementation of the first actions. This structuring, based on existing programmes, has led to the support of the most mature projects in terms of the relationship between science and society and to the emergence of new dynamics that will be supported by future actions.

The University's SAPS/SWAFS policy focuses on the actions planned in the SUNSET project and more broadly integrates the public relations and scientific culture components already underway. The transversal positioning of the team in charge of the SAPS/SWAFS programme allows the coordination of all actions related to the SAPS/SWAFS policy. This includes recurring science outreach programmes (My thesis in 180sec, European Researchers' Night, Bordeaux Science Tour, etc.), publicity for ANR (Agence National de la Recherche) funded projects, participation in Enlight RISE, as well as support and advice for new science and society projects carried out by UB units or external partners and submitted to the SAPS team. In this context, a team dedicated to the implementation of the SAPS/SWAFS programme has become the focal point for RISE. This team has developed internal links with an internal community of interest with 350 referents.

In 2023 and 2024, 2 university staff have participated in the webinars organised by RISE:

ENLIGHT-PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT WEBINAR 1: SCIENCE SHOPS (Thursday, 22nd June 2023)
Dr Henk Mulder will explain how the Science Shops at the University of Groningen are operating. Science Shops are the offices that broker research requests from the non-profit sector to students and staff, and in that way, facilitate the co-production of knowledge (consultancy-type citizen science). The University of Groningen has 5 Science Shops in different faculties (since 1979) and collaborates in a 6th Science Shop with another University and the Municipality. Dr Mulder has been working for the Science Shop since 1989 and is co-founder of Living Knowledge, the International Science Shop Network.

ENLIGHT-Public Engagement Webinar 5: Impact in Academia, Thursday, 25th January 2024
In this webinar, representatives of the ENLIGHT Impact Task Force will introduce the concept of impact: what is impact? what is not impact? what is impact assessment? and what is the link with societal engagement? They will also present the ENLIGHT methodology for the impact assessment of university activities and discuss with participants how to embed an impact-driven culture at ENLIGHT universities and beyond.

Actions Per Section

1 - Citizen Science, towards societal transitions

The aim is to strengthen the ongoing dialogue with society, to better take into account public policies and citizens' needs for research on societal challenges. As part of its Transitions Policy and its national research agency ACT program, UB is setting up Living Labs, which aim at transforming the university into an open laboratory in the city, where people can work together to solve environmental et societal challenges. Support from the SAPS/SWAFS policy has enabled the Living Labs to be fed with scientific mediation and participatory science initiatives, particularly around the issues of urban forests and nature in the city. This strand has also enabled 170 young secondary school students to take part in the "COP27 Lycéenne Régionale" operation, in conjunction with the UB's urban nature projects.

The RISE programme also enabled the organisation of a "Science Shop" workshop on 10 October 2024. Attended by 15 university staff and partners (including the CSTI Cap Science), this workshop, chaired by Prof. Henk Mulder and organised by the SAPS programme team at the university, was an introduction to public engagement and how Science Shop works. It took place in the Science and Technology Library. This is part of the ongoing Citizen Science plan at the University and was organised to start discussions. A future working group - open to SAPS project partners - will be organised to write and create a Citizen Science roadmap for the university.

2- Working with schoolchildren and inspiring a desire for science

Given the challenges of raising young people's awareness of science, particularly in the light of recent surveys showing a certain mistrust of science, this strand is part of a context in which young people's scientific culture, and, above all, their knowledge of the scientific method needs stimulating. It also raises the issue of democratising access to scientific careers, with its attendant inequalities in terms of gender, social level and geographical location.

During this first year, coordination with the various players involved (Rectorat, Cap Sciences, Maison pour la Science, etc.) has enabled us to take stock of existing initiatives aimed at schoolchildren and to identify local needs. Discussions with the UB's research staff and

partners then enabled a single entry point to be established via the SAPS/SWAFS project team and operational coordination, particularly for the Bordeaux academy. The field activities carried out with Cap Sciences have reached 580 schoolchildren (14 classes and 16 researchers via the "one class, one researcher" programme). The remote workshop will rapidly complement these interactions and reinforce the work on the scientific approach. In terms of discovering university career paths, support for certain schools has enabled them to take part in campus activities (Lamapiens Collegians Congress, Maths Week).

Strand 3 - Promoting research, science and heritage.

The actions in this strand aim at strengthening scientific influence and the dissemination of CSTI, and at highlighting the answers provided by science to current societal challenges. This involves : (i) setting up new interfaces with the public, without hesitating to go into the public arena - (ii) facilitating the public's appropriation of methods, recent advances in science and technical developments - (iii) enlightening this approach by opening up scientific heritage more widely, in conjunction with the region's cultural players. The creation of a cabinet of curiosities at Cap Science is just one stage in the process of promoting the UB's heritage collections to the general public and schoolchildren. Other projects include (i) a first photographic exhibition planned for November 2023, inaugurating a new large-format display system (twenty panels on the gates of the Talence campus, Cours de la Libération) - (ii) the acquisition of showcases for travelling exhibitions, with a first on the site of the new "Droit - Lettres" library - (iii) the formalisation of an institutional partnership with the Aquitaine Museum, materialised by a joint working group aimed at co-constructing new initiatives.

Strand 4 - Democratising knowledge and combating infodemia.

By definition, the university is a privileged forum for academic debate, with genuine legitimacy and ethical principles that provide the insight needed to make choices and take positions on major societal issues, above and beyond partisan posturing. The initiatives in this strand are based on this observation to inform citizens, give them the keys to understanding and enable them to play a real role in our society in transition (initiatives aimed at the media, debates on social issues). This part of the programme also aims to overcome a certain mistrust of science, particularly among young people, as shown by recent surveys (debates in secondary schools, promotion of science and scientific careers among young people). Finally, the democratisation of science and the fight against social, territorial and gender inequalities require in-depth work, which we tackle through direct contact in the classroom, with a focus on targets that are usually far removed from the academic world.

Strand 5 - Training: mediation, participatory science and open data

The aim of this strand is to make the staff of the institution and its partners more aware of the issues surrounding science and society, to encourage their involvement in sharing knowledge and taking account of society's needs, and to integrate this culture into their initial training. This long-term project involves collective reflection on scientific mediation and writing. Some of these have already taken place and others will emerge over the coming year, such as a SAPS summer school. Training initiatives are scheduled to begin in 2023, including a dedicated 'Bordeaux campus' workshop on participatory science. At the same time, work has already begun on the organisation of training for doctoral students.

In order to better train PhD students and push them to undertake new citizen science initiatives, a SAPS career pack will be proposed to them within a few months. Several career packs are already offered to those students with the aim of adding a new expertise in their curriculum, all as part of the University of Bordeaux Graduate Research School (UBGRS 2.0). The training will rely on practical dissemination actions aimed at the general public or schoolchildren, construction of participatory science projects or specific illustration or writing workshops.

FUTURE

Since 2023, the SAPS/SAWFS team has been staffed by 3 people who work in close collaboration with the university's various departments (research department, cultural services, college of doctoral schools, documentation department, institute of transitions) and partners, to support the development of the 5 areas mentioned above. The science and society policy are overseen by a mission officer, who is a member of the governance team and works to ensure the long-term viability of the SAPS/SAWFS policy throughout the university.

For the Université de Bordeaux, the ENLIGHT alliance is an opportunity to continue sharing best practices on missions as essential as public engagement activities, and with universities that are particularly advanced in these areas.

Comenius University Bratislava

Comenius University Bratislava is the largest university in Slovakia has 13 faculties with currently more than 22000 students; offers study programmes in a wide spectrum of disciplines ranging from art and humanities (including theology), through law, economics and social sciences, natural sciences, mathematics, information sciences to medicine. CU is research intensive; our researchers participate in top-level research in a number of scientific disciplines.

However, with a focus on Public Engagement activities, the scale and decentralised structure of the institution has resulted in a disconnection between the faculties and their respective activities, as well as between the faculties and the central offices. Despite its methodical guidance from the top management and central offices at the rectorate, each faculty operates its research agenda independently.

BEFORE RISE

Prior to the ENLIGHT RISE project, the university had not mapped any of its Public Engagement (PE) activities, nor did it provide any central or faculty support infrastructure (e.g., office/networking/events/guidelines) for activities related to this topic. However, the WP6 mapping exercise (published as deliverable D6.1), enabled the university to consolidate knowledge about PE activities and projects across all 14 faculties. Despite the absence of institutional guidance and policy on PE, numerous public engagement activities were discovered.

For example:

The Faculty of Law at Comenius University Bratislava has established the Student Legal Counselling Office to improve the preparation of law students for legal practice. Under the guidance of supervisors from faculty members or experts in the field, students offer free legal analysis to clients of the counselling office. This initiative effectively combines the teaching process of law students with the provision of socially useful legal assistance to the disadvantaged population.

Additionally, CPP FiF (The Centre for Scholarship and Teaching at the Faculty of Arts) provides training to teachers through international collaboration and mutual dialogue. This training aims to equip teachers with innovative, impactful, and inclusive teaching methods to be further used in schools.

Thanks to the mapping we, at the central offices made an assessment of popular public engagement practices at our university and created an internal mailing list for targeted training offers etc.

DURING RISE

During the ENLIGHT RISE project, the institution derived substantial benefits from the formation of a community of practice mailing list for PE practitioners and enthusiasts, thanks to which we were able to localize more researchers interested in PE. The WP6 mailing list created a lasting community of practice through the provision of webinars, filling the gaps that existed within the university's infrastructure and offering necessary know-how and opportunities for international networking in the field of PE. The extensive discussions on various PE topics and expert webinars enabled the community to leverage public engagement practice.

In the fall of 2023, Dr. Henk Mulder delivered a lecture on building a Public Engagement community of practice at the University of Groningen to researchers from various faculties and staff members at Comenius University, Bratislava. During the lecture, Dr. Mulder emphasized the importance of Public Engagement in research, by sharing his experiences, lessons learned, and good practices from his university. The lecture was well-received and helped to further strengthen our efforts in creating a stable PE community at our university.

FUTURE

Comenius University Bratislava still has a long way to go in establishing a sustainable PE infrastructure at the university level. Nonetheless, the institution aims to build on the lessons learned during the ENLIGHT RISE project by creating institutional workshops for its PhD students and PhD supervisors at the CU PhD school. The university also plans to maintain an internal mailing list for PE practitioners, which will facilitate the growth of the institutional PE network and enable a sustainable approach to mutual in-house learning.

To establish a sustainable PE infrastructure model at Comenius University Bratislava, external best practices shared by fostering webinars and workshops among all ENLIGHT universities will be considered. These will be organised as an agenda of a PE expert network, which will be created as continuity of the ENLIGHT RISE activities after the project ends.

University of Galway

By Ruth Hynes, Office of the Vice-President of Research and Innovation

BEFORE RISE

Before RISE, we at University of Galway had a broad portfolio of engagement activity across the organisation. Engagement activities were informally connected operating organically across the organisation, based mainly on informal communities of practice and some centralised units.

There was a particular focus on community engagement through our Community Knowledge Initiative (a centralised unit), on Public Patient Involvement in our research activities across the healthcare domain, on Science Outreach through public engagement projects and festivals, our research communications and training programme Threesis, on industry engagement through our research centres and Innovation Office, and on public engagement through our museums of zoology, computers and geology.

This sense of engagement with the external world in research and innovation was reflected in our values of openness and respect and embedded in the university strategy 2020-2025 [Shared-Vision, Shaped by Values.](#)

Flagship actions with the strategy included the following:

- "We will strive to make a positive impact on society through partnering with other universities, organisations and communities, locally and internationally, to enable the creation and sharing of knowledge, expertise and technologies."
- "We will design and implement a structured programme of engagement for strategic external stakeholders, including alumni, industry, community and government, to benefit from advice, expertise, support and engagement"
- "We will embed engaged research across the University by involving and collaborating with the public throughout the process of our research activities."

DURING RISE

The Research and Innovation Strategy, Purpose People Place, was published in October 2021 and had a page dedicated to engagement and collaboration as an exemplar of how we see our 'People'.

Furthermore, the Research and Innovation strategy committed to:

- Fully integrate engagement and impact into research development and assessment.
- Embed engaged research across the University by involving and collaborating with the public throughout the process of our research activities.

These strategic ambitions, and underpinning actions, have run in parallel with our involvement in RISE.

Adaptions post-Covid

From 2021 onward (just as RISE was on the rise) there were some significant changes to methodologies in public engagement practice. We were incorporating online approaches to communication and events, which gave way to new methodologies in public engagement practice.

New networks and learnings in Europe

This online environment also allowed for great engagement across the Enlight network and in the RISE project. We reached out to our internal community to bring them into the ENLIGHT-PE-community.

As part of the RISE webinar series, in November 2023, Dr. Lorraine Tansey outlined how the Community Knowledge Initiative at the University of Galway collaborates with community partners for teaching and learning opportunities. Also covered was the co-founding of the national Irish higher education network for civic engagement Campus Engage. This webinar focuses on current academic modules that connect students with migrant rights groups across Galway city in order to build understanding of diversity and inclusion. Equally valuable were the other webinars from our RISE partners which were informative and can be used to shape the thinking of our research community into the future. We also had the opportunity to network in person with colleagues in Galway during the meeting in June 2022.

Existing and new projects

During this time, the EPE team in CÚRAM launched two new public engagement platforms, through exhibitions in the Galway Atalantiquaria and the Galway Museum. The team also continued to excel through the creation of award-winning documentaries, teachers-in-residence programmes and artist-in-resident programmes.

Our research community continued to be successful in the Science Foundation Ireland Discovery programme, with excellent projects including ReelLife Science, funded as part of the programme.

The Galway Science and Technology Festival brought to campus over 20,000 visitors, the largest one-day celebration of science in Ireland.

Threesis, the research communications training programme and competition led by the Office of the Vice-President for Research and Innovation, brought to a public audience in a packed auditorium 3-minute talks by our PhD students.

The Insight Centre for Data Analytics continued to welcome visitors to Ireland's only Computer Museum, reopening after Covid.

The work of PPI continued and grew to a national programme and is now formally embedded in the university's flagship BioInnovate programme.

The move towards challenge-based research emphasises engaged research, as evident at national and EU levels, and we embedded engagement in the university Galway Global Challenges programme launched in 2021.

Capacity building

During this timeframe, a number of university staff participated in the Irish University Association's six-week train-the-trainer course in "Engaged Research for Societal Impact capacity-building workshops. This has allowed new learnings to be brought back into the university and this is being fed into online and in-person supports for the research community.

In parallel with a growing focus at a government level on evidence-based policy, the university has run a series of seminars focused on engagement with policy makers.

We also saw the emphasis on evidence-informed public policy, with the Public Consultation on a Higher Education Research Policy Engagement Framework in September 2023, into which some of the community of practice contributed.

FUTURE

This WP has allowed us to compare ourselves internationally and benchmark our activity in this area. We have also had many learnings and want to continue to support our research community in PE.

As champions of knowledge and innovation, universities must not only create ground-breaking research but also ensure its ultimate impact. To achieve this, we need to foster a research impact culture where all members of our research community can recognize and contribute to the transformative potential of research. This means supporting, recognising and rewarding researchers as they plan, capture, communicate and monitor impact. In many disciplines, an engaged approach to research has emerged as an enabler of impact.

For our research community, engaged research needs to be a strong element to underpin and achieve research impact. We need to train researchers in basic skills, offer engagement opportunities, and support/seed further engagements. Efforts are already underway to support our research community in this area, but more needs to be done.

There are many stepping stones to engagement, and we will support our research community as they take initial small steps in this direction.

Fundamental to research impact and engagement with the wider world is communication.

Our researchers need to be supported in every way possible, under the usual constraints, to communicate their research embracing the university brand and ethos.

As part of capacity building into the future, we will need to be informed thoroughly by the researcher viewpoint. The term engagement means different things to different people within the organisation, with a cross-over and between engaged research, science communication, marketing, public relations, PPI, stakeholder engagement, public affairs, policy formation and schools' liaison.

For example, we plan to:

- Continue the community of practice.
- Look for ways to coordinate activity in Galway and with partners.
- Support capacity building in the area of research into policy and engagement with policymakers.
- Provide training on stakeholder mapping and engaged research.
- Explore seed-funding initiatives to encourage and reward engaged research and PE.
- Co-develop case studies providing exemplars of engaged research.
- Continue to support industry engagement through the Innovation Office and other touch points.
- Increase communication and public engagement capabilities.
- Create a forum for the research community, including PhD students, to plug into the existing public engagement activities and nurture a community of practice.
- Continue to develop resources via the Research Community Portal on engagement and Research Communications.

Ghent University

Input is gathered from Ghent University staff: Jolien Coenraets, Bastiaan Baccarne, Charlotte Cailliau, Alien Masson, David De Wolf, Femke Lootens, Riet Van de Velde, Irene Govaert, Esther De Smet, Floor Verhaeghe, Charlotte Prové, Alexis Dewaele, Jeroen Bourgonjon.

BEFORE RISE

Before the RISE project, Ghent University promoted Public Engagement through a variety of initiatives:

- i) A dual structure of Societal and Economic Interdisciplinary Consortia
 - a. Societal liaison network of 10 interdisciplinary consortia ([IDC consortia](#))
 - b. Industrial liaison network of 26 business development consortia ([IOE consortia](#)); some also work with master's thesis studios, and/or focus on a broader group of stakeholders (policy, etc.) than just industry - for example, one of the 26 consortia recently organized the energy festival ([EnergyFest](#))
- ii) Platforms that foster network opportunities such as
 - a. Ghent University Museum ([GUM](#))
 - b. Dare To Venture (entrepreneurship centre for students and researchers) ([DO!](#)) (who facilitate the '[call for challenges](#)'; see below)
 - c. Strategic collaborations with the city of Ghent: COMON, De Krook, living labs, ...
- iii) Communicative actions focusing on public engagement such as
 - a. Webpage on '[Science communication](#)': science bar, science cafes, Citizen science projects, museum GUM, educational offer for teachers and students, Dag van de Wetenschap
 - b. Online magazine with stories of Ghent University students, staff and alumni ([Dare To Think](#))
 - c. FUTUREproef award ([FUTURE proef](#))
- iv) Actions in education to connect students to jointly work on problems defined by civil society, such as
 - a. [Call for challenges](#): a challenge from outside the university which is tackled by several students from across the university working in multi-disciplinary teams.

These initiatives are embedded in Ghent University policy and strategic plan(s), which underlines the support of Ghent University's leadership for these initiatives.

Promoting Public Engagement through Interdisciplinary Consortia at Ghent University.

Ghent University is committed to fostering interdisciplinary collaboration and maximizing the societal impact of research through its ten research consortia, known as IDC (Interdisciplinary Consortia). They focus on diverse important topics such as crime prevention, mental health, the labour market, globalization, cultural heritage, human rights, an ageing population,

technological innovations, migration, and urban challenges. These consortia play a pivotal role in supporting public engagement and contributing to real-world change.

Here are some key features that highlight their dedication to societal impact and public engagement:

1. Dedicated Funding for Societal Impact:

The IDC are funded through Ghent University's Special Research Fund, emphasizing their commitment to societal impact. This distinctive funding source distinguishes them from Business Development Centres, which primarily focus on economic impact through funding from the Industrial Research Fund.

2. Interdisciplinary Collaboration and Beyond:

Interdisciplinarity lies at the heart of the IDC initiative, fostering collaboration not only within faculties but also across the spectrum of Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) and Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics, and Medicine (STEMM). Furthermore, the consortia prioritize transdisciplinarity and co-creation by actively engaging with non-academic stakeholders. The general public is one of those key stakeholders and as such public engagement, is a key ingredient for achieving societal impact.

3. Knowledge Brokerage and Collaboration:

The IDC coordinator functions as a knowledgeable broker, facilitating collaboration between consortium members and working closely with the central Research Department as well as key stakeholders. This collaboration extends to shaping societal impact policies both locally (community based initiatives) as well as internationally. The success of the IDC initiative is underscored by its recognition as a best practice on the EU Knowledge Valorisation Platform, further validating its contribution to advancing interdisciplinary collaboration, supporting public engagement, and promoting real-world impact.

DURING RISE

During the RISE project, Ghent University has benefited from participating in Work Package 6 in several ways: i) it helped to boost new initiatives that coincided with the Rise project, ii) it strengthened existing initiatives, and iii) it offered a platform for networking and learning opportunities.

Rise coincided with the establishment of a new website of Ghent University to provide more transparency for companies and also for organizations on the possible ways of collaborating with Ghent University. The scope is very broad, but all relate to Public Engagement: from

working with students in thesis and other projects, to making use of Ghent University equipment for measurements etc.

Rise also coincided with the start of industrial liaison officer for the faculties of Social Sciences, Humanities and Arts. Rise offered an opportunity for the liaison to bring the Industrial liaison network closer to the Societal liaison network by using Public Engagement as a building block. The liaison's participation in the ENLIGHT Public Engagement List facilitated 'on-the-job learning' and provided an opportunity to build a network both within the University and with partner university in the ENLIGHT alliance. Indeed, the webinars that were organized in WP 6 provided a source of inspiration as well as a platform to exchange views with colleagues in the ENLIGHT alliance.

The impact of Rise Work Package 6 impact on Ghent University Interdisciplinary consortia.

As the Ghent University consortia embarked on their journey to push the boundaries of interdisciplinary collaboration, a pivotal chapter unfolded with the implementation of WP6 within the framework of the RISE project. WP6, embedded in the RISE project, was strategically designed to foster international collaboration and knowledge exchange. The IDC consortia used its potential to amplify their interdisciplinary initiatives and contribute to societal impact. To give some specific examples:

The PSYNC consortium, dedicated to advancing mental health research, embarked on a journey of enhanced communication and collaboration being levered by WP6 activities. The PSYNC coordinator's membership in the ENLIGHT Public Engagement List facilitated communication among members. Their active participation in the Enlight-public engagement webinar, "Impact of Science Communication," proved pivotal. Valuable insights were gleaned, particularly in the assessment of science communication, empowering PSYNC to refine their strategies for impactful public engagement. Furthermore, PSYNC actively collaborated with Ghent University and other ENLIGHT partners, including the University of Groningen, University of Göttingen, and Comenius University. Together, they submitted the project proposal titled "The Age of Inclusion. Transformations of Urban Belonging in an Ageing Europe." Although the project did not secure funding, its focus on engaging stakeholders and end-users showcased the consortium's commitment to meaningful societal impact and public engagement.

The Stadsacademie, a collaborative hub addressing wicked sustainability issues in Ghent, found a unique niche within WP6 as a regional academy. This positioning provided a platform for fruitful exchanges with other regional academies within ENLIGHT, enhancing their understanding and approach to regional sustainability challenges. Moreover, the consortium's active participation opened up opportunities for transdisciplinary education at

Ghent University, aligning with ENLIGHT's ethos of breaking down academic silos and fostering holistic learning experiences.

The Centre for the Social Study of Migration and Refugees (CESSMIR) embarked on a transformative journey within WP6, culminating in impactful recognitions. The CESSMIR coordinator actively participated in an ENLIGHT Public Engagement webinar, enriching their understanding of effective engagement strategies. Notably, CESSMIR director Ilse Derluyn's outstanding contributions were celebrated with an impact award at the ENLIGHT Impact Conference. Recognizing her exceptional impact, Ilse Derluyn is now an ENLIGHT Impact Ambassador, further amplifying the consortium's influence. The course 'Migration and Society,' offered by CESSMIR, received prestigious acknowledgment with an ENLIGHT Teaching & Learning Award in 2022, showcasing their commitment to excellence in education within the realm of migration studies.

Through this collaboration, PSYNC, the Stadsacademie, and CESSMIR demonstrated how the strategic utilization of WP6 within the ENLIGHT framework not only facilitated effective communication but also empowered them to refine their public engagement strategies, embrace regional sustainability challenges, and excel in impactful teaching and learning within the evolving landscape of academia and societal impact.

FUTURE

After the RISE project, Ghent University will continue its investment in the activities related to public engagement as outlined above. This year, 2024, marks the start of a renewed 5-year strategic plan of our Technology Transfer Office. The strategic plan outlines four key objectives, of which two relate very closely to public engagement: to broaden the activities related to Flipped TTO (demand pull rather than technology push) and to expand our science parks. For example, one of the operational objectives is to strengthen the collaboration between the tenants at the science parks and our researchers. Similarly, last year the policy framework for Societal impact of research at Ghent University was renewed in which Public Engagement is integrated as part of research impact.

Public Engagement will remain at the core of the IDC.

As the RISE project approaches its conclusion, the IDC consortia at Ghent University are laying the groundwork for a future marked by sustained and strengthened public engagement. Their initiatives are poised to transcend the RISE project, ensuring a lasting impact on societal connection and collaboration.

1. Empowering the Next Generation:

The commitment to public engagement echoes through the launch of a new UGent initiative – a starter's guide to societal impact course tailored for young researchers. With a specific focus on public engagement, this course is designed to equip emerging scholars with the tools and insights needed to integrate societal impact into their research endeavours. By nurturing a culture of engagement from the outset, these consortia aim to cultivate a generation of researchers who are inherently attuned to the importance of connecting their work with broader audiences.

2. DELTA's Pursuit of Excellence:

DELTA, a dynamic consortium within this collaborative tapestry, is gearing up to submit a proposal for the prestigious ENLIGHT impact award. Their aspirations are anchored in tangible efforts to involve a larger audience in the development of technological innovations. By channelling their endeavours toward this award, DELTA exemplifies the commitment to not only creating impactful innovations but also fostering an inclusive approach, engaging diverse stakeholders in the innovation process. Winning this award would not only be a recognition of their current efforts but also a springboard for future initiatives that place public engagement at the forefront of technological advancements.

3. Strategic Aims for Sustained Engagement:

Beyond individual initiatives, there is a collective and strategic commitment among all consortia to sustain and fortify public engagement. This commitment is articulated through a multifaceted approach that encompasses science communication, events, and ongoing research projects. By weaving public engagement into the very fabric of their strategic aims, these consortia are poised to sustain a dynamic relationship with the public. This forward-thinking approach ensures that public engagement is not merely a project-based endeavour but an integral and enduring aspect of their scholarly pursuits.

In essence, the consortia at Ghent University are not viewing the conclusion of the RISE project as an endpoint but rather as a transition to a future where public engagement remains a central tenet of their collaborative efforts. Through empowering the next generation, striving for excellence in innovation, and strategically embedding public engagement in their ongoing initiatives, these consortia are poised to shape a future where the dialogue between academia and society continues to flourish.

University of Göttingen

BEFORE RISE

Prior to our engagement in ENLIGHT RISE, key aspects of our public engagement activities are:

- **The University Collections:** in close collaboration with ENLIGHT partners in Gent and Uppsala, we spent over ten years developing the Museum of Knowledge in the Forum Wissen at the University of Göttingen. Before this museum opened in 2022, our university collections were only barely accessible to the public, with limited possibilities of interaction. Today, the Forum Wissen has 60.000 annual visitors. It is a place in which knowledge is conveyed, reflected upon, discussed and created. We help to facilitate social exchange and create spaces in which people with different perspectives can learn from one another. By these means we play an active role in science communication. The Museum of Knowledge in the Forum Wissen is the first museum in Germany to focus on the process of knowledge creation and to create opportunities for the general public to influence scientific research. As the official museum of the University of Göttingen, we are directly involved in current research projects from a variety of academic disciplines, and, together with the many institutions that make up the Göttingen campus, form part of an international network. In our exhibitions, we make the unique objects that belong to the approximately 40 decentralised collections of the University accessible to the general public. These are worthy of preservation, as they testify to 300 years of scientific history. We are currently nominated for the 2024 European Museum of the Year award. Marjan Doom, head of Ghent university museum, is a member of the advisory board.
- **Large Outreach Events:** The University presents itself to the public in our full breadth of teaching and research at the IdeenExpo - a Germany-wide, successful co-operation between business, science and politics to promote the next generation of skilled workers – and the biannual Göttingen Night of Science, where almost everything the University has to offer awaits visitors. Whether it's microscopy, agricultural science, mathematics, economics or University Sports, advice on all aspects of studying, campus tours, theatre, lectures or sign language puzzles - there's something for all ages. We expect over 25.000 visitors to each event.
- **Individual Outreach Events:** During the semester, we have daily events which are open to the public, ranging from public lectures to concerts and research-centred events addressing families.

- **Schools:** Our xLab, yLab and BLAB invite school students from Göttingen schools to research-oriented courses in the sciences and humanities.

DURING RISE

In ENLIGHT and ENLIGHT RISE, our main project-related activities in public engagement were:

- **The ENLIGHT Lectures Series:** This was a format inspired by the COVID pandemic, and the inability to host public events by inviting researchers from partner universities. Born out of a lack, it turned out to be a key asset: we invited up to four researchers nearly every month from different partner universities to present their research to a public audience online. The lecturers are specifically told to address an interested lay audience and asked not to become too technical in their lectures. None of these researchers would have been given the opportunity to meet and interact without this context. The person organising the lectures, Aleksandra Bovt, was the University of Göttingen's contact point in the communication group and represented Göttingen in the ENLIGHT RISE Public engagement work package. The YouTube videos have cumulatively received several thousand views.
- - o Format of the Lecture
 - For each ENLIGHT Focus Area, there are around four ENLIGHT Lectures
 - Each lecture has a topic with appeal to a public audience.
 - Online format via zoom with live stream on YouTube
 - Duration: maximum of 70 minutes, 4-5 speakers, each from a different ENLIGHT partner and each speaking for 5-10 minutes on the topic, followed by a discussion between the scientists
 - The 4 individual lectures should include a focus on current cutting edge research projects within ENLIGHT in this field, research-oriented student-led project(s), best practice example(s) from one of the regions (not all within the same lecture, but each lecture could put one such project into the foreground)
 - Introduction and moderation by either an experienced person from the public relations or IO offices, one prominent and experienced member of the scientific community or a student
 - There is a Question and Answer session with the audience at the end of each lecture. Questions are written into the comment section by all those who are attending the lecture on zoom, and the moderator then puts these questions to the lecturers.

- We could include the cross-linking of and with the regions by for example holding lectures at places that are connected to the topic. One example could be that an IT specialist will talk in front of a supercomputer.
 - In between the semesters, and interdisciplinary “Holiday Lecture” will be organized to connect the topics from past and upcoming lecture series.
- Each lecture was followed by a networking event for the scientific community. In the brand-new virtual space, the researchers from ENLIGHT universities can not only continue the discussion on the lecture’s topic but also use the opportunity to identify common research interests. This event serves as a platform for developing new ideas for future cooperation within the network.
- ENLIGHT lecture titles:
 - Future of Energy
 - Circular Economy & Environment
 - Health & Sustainability
 - Sustainable Cities/Smart Cities
 - Artificial Intelligence: ethical aspects
 - Smart Systems & Robotics
 - Digital Revolution & Society
 - Forests in Time of Climate Change
 - Food, Diet and Sustainability
 - Tackling Climate Change: The Humanities Perspective
 - Climate Change: Art, Performance & Narration
 - Migration & Climate Change
 - Equity & Society
 - Equity in Science & Technology
 - Health & Equity
 - Health & Sustainability
 - Urban Health
 - Health & Digitalization

Composition and Concert: Vivaldi Four Seasons in Climate Change

Inspired by current and projected climate data and already visible consequences of climate change on flora and fauna, Antonio Vivaldi's work "The Four Seasons" was reinterpreted by **Prof. Dr. Mark Barden** (Professor of Composition, Detmold University of Music) with the assistance of the composition students Carlo Tosato, Zara Ali and Daniel Kalantari. Scientific

insights were provided by **Prof. Dr. Alexander Knohl** (Professor of Bioclimatology, Faculty of Forest Sciences and Forest Ecology, University of Göttingen) and **ENLIGHT** researchers.

In cooperation with the **Göttingen Baroque Orchestra (Conductor Antonius Adamske)** the new composition „Die Vier Jahreszeiten im (Klima)Wandel / The Four Seasons in (Climate) Change“ premiered on **9th of September 2022** in concert, at the **Assembly Hall of the University of Göttingen**. In between the four concert movements, Prof. Knohl and his colleagues explained the influence of climate change on the seasons as well as Prof. Barden and his composition team provided a general explanation of how the scientific findings on climate change were taken into account in the development of the new composition.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=imnvOAPOYN0>

- **Forum Wissen:** Current joint project with the University of Ghent to commission an art object to be shown in both cities.
- **ENLIGHT at the Göttingen Night of Sciences:** in 2022, one of the stands at the Göttingen Night of Science was dedicated to ENLIGHT. We invited the interested public to inform themselves about the network, its partners and activities, also focussing on research collaboration as intended in ENLIGHT RISE. In order to attract families, children were invited to build the ENLIGHT lighthouse by stacking large, coloured boxes in the correct order.
- **Participation in ENLIGHT events:** members of the Public Relations Departments of the University of Göttingen participated in ENLIGHT science events, in particular two sessions of the IMPACT Labs.
- **Open Science:** The University of Göttingen lead the work package on Open Science in ENLIGHT RISE, and as such, as responsible for the endeavours of increasing accessibility to research publications.

FUTURE

How do we intend to sustain or even strengthen public engagement after RISE?

- **Forum Wissen:** we intend to find more projects that utilise the ENLIGHT cooperation for exhibitions and projects at the Forum Wissen. We are currently expanding the Forum Wissen to include a culture form (with a planetarium) and a Biodiversity Museum. This will give us further ways to connect our public engagement activities with our ENLIGHT partners, for instance, in our recently developed, third-party funded sustainable citizen science efforts focussing on Nature Conservation Biology.

- **Lecture Series:** The use of digital tools to offer a greater number of public lectures in an international context has inspired us. It is an ideal format to show our global engagement and research affiliations with scientists around the world while at the same time saving on emission-intensive travel.
- **ENLIGHT at the Göttingen Night of Sciences:** Building on the high interest in 2022, presenting ENLIGHT at the Night of Sciences will be an established part of this large outreach event.
- **Peer Review:** we look forward to continuous exchange with our colleagues from the ENLIGHT network engaged in public relations, learning from one another and broadening our activities.
- **Dissemination:** in the ENLIGHT network, we can all make use of each other's dissemination channels and reach much broader audiences.

University of Groningen

By Henk Mulder, with input from Quin Genee and Ana Ranitovic

BEFORE RISE

Before RISE there were already many structures and activities, but they were done on their own 'islands'. Some are 'traditional' science communication or outreach, other activities are higher on the Ladder of Participation, and are therefore more focused on engagement and dialogue/interaction.

[Websites](#) / [Podcasts](#) : showcasing UG Research and Education.
[Studium Generale](#) (presentations and discussion) / [Science Cafés](#) / [Mindwise](#) (website and debates)
Events: [Researchers Night](#) / [Weekend of Science](#) / [Publics' Academy](#) in [various faculties](#)
Cultural: [University Museum](#) / [University Cultural Center](#)
Science Center: [Science LinX](#) : activities at/in collaboration with Science LinX: [Discovery Truck](#) / [Outreach Activities](#) / [Events](#) / [Teacher Support](#) / [Expositions](#) / [Citizen Science](#) ([CurioUs](#) / [Meet-o-Theek](#)) / [Blauw Observatory](#) / [PE Projects](#)
For Schools: [High School Students' Support](#) / [Science Knot-Children's University](#)
Living Labs: [Campus Fryslan](#), [Green Office](#)
Consultancy: [Science Shops](#) / [Legal Advice Services](#)
Citizen Science Projects (various faculties, no central website)
4 [Multi-disciplinary Schools](#) (Public Health; Energy; Sustainability; Digital Society) with [hackathons](#), the [Public Participation Center](#), [touring exhibitions](#) and events, projects and programmes in [House of Connections](#)

RISE coincided with the establishment of our new strategic plan, [Making Connections](#). UG's mission states ... *UG operates internationally and uses its innovative strength to tackle scientific and societal challenges and to train global citizens. Moreover, the University engages with the local region and makes an active contribution to strengthening and shaping the regional knowledge ecosystem.*

RISE also coincided with the start of our [Open Science Program](#), which includes a [Public Engagement Pillar](#).

Based on our strategic plan, also the four multi-disciplinary schools on the grand societal challenges were further established¹, to foster transdisciplinary and engaged research, education, and impact focused on the grand societal challenges.

¹ One of them already existed before the start of ENLIGHT RISE, the other three were planned and established during RISE.

DURING RISE

Even though the main activity for UG during RISE was to share our expertise on Public Engagement², RISE also offered us time (and additional connections) to connect our internal activities and establish a UG PE-network (now with over 80 people), as part of our Open Science Programme. For this, a PE steering group was established. This was first chaired by the Director of the University Museum, and later by the Impact Office.

The following activities were undertaken:

1. [Update and publish a UG vision on public engagement](#)

We based our vision on the definition given by the National Coordinating Centre for Public Engagement in the UK, which emphasizes that public engagement is by definition a two-way street.

2. [Set up a public engagement community for information exchange between UG/UMCG initiatives](#)

We connected the individuals at the various departments through networking events. The first two were relatively modest, with 8 to 12 people participating, and introducing themselves and their organization. The third meeting was for the whole Open Science Community and drew about 40 participants. The most recent activity was a workshop for all university staff and researchers/teachers, which drew about 45 participants. Here, we had a guest speaker from the National Coordinating Centre for Public Engagement (UK) explain the PE activities of British universities, as an example. Other workshops included the start of a Citizen Science Network at UG, a training for researchers on how to draw up proposals for Science Communication Grants, and a workshop on Recognition and Rewards for PE. The mailing list for Public Engagement Professionals at UG now has over 80 participants (Feb 2024).

3. [Develop University-wide training for secretaries](#)

We also developed a workshop for secretaries (the gatekeepers to our research groups) to make sure that they were supported in connecting questions that they receive from societal stakeholders to the right researchers or departments. After identifying the group that would benefit from a training in public engagement, they were consulted on what their needs were and how they would like it to be addressed. Based on this information, a trainer was asked to develop a tailor-made training. This was piloted with 8 secretaries and communication officers. Based on their feedback the setup of the training was finalized.

² UG staff organized workshops for the other partners in Bilbao, Bordeaux, Bratislava and Groningen, and organized four of the six PE-Webinars.

During the national secretary day, the training was offered as a workshop within the UG and about 15 participants participated. The training was repeated in September 2023.

4. [Set up a network, and pilot academic training sessions, to support and professionalize staff in their public engagement activities \(e.g. citizen science\)](#)

Based on surveys and follow-up interviews it became clear to us that many researchers want to share their fascination for research. The bottleneck for them is 'how to' do this, next to time and rewards. Therefore, eight workshops were developed with public engagement experts from different UG faculties and services, as well as with external experts. The topics covered include scientific storytelling, making a podcast, use of social media, thinking like a journalist, planning for and creating impact, presenting your impact, and story mapping.

5. [Plan and pilot a call for seed funding](#)

Finally, we offered seed funding for those researchers who wanted to set up an engagement project in collaboration with a civil society partner.

The criteria and assessment procedure were established, and 27 applications were received in the first call, with 7 meeting the selection criteria. After evaluation, the criteria were modified for clarity, resulting in 17 applications for the second call, with 10 meeting the criteria. The second round explicitly required an external partner and a new PE activity.

In total, 9 projects received funding of up to 5000 Euro, reflecting an improvement in engaging the public and promoting PE activities within UG and UMCG. It was suggested that future seed funding calls should allow for a longer application time to accommodate more comprehensive proposals.

We hope that these researchers will be able to base a larger application (e.g. to the National Call for Science Communication), based on their experience in this seeded project. To give additional visibility to the topic of public engagement, the UG Open Science team has dedicated the 2024 season of its podcast series "[Open Science Bites](#)" to spotlighting the recipients.

Additionally, via our [Ben Feringa Impact Award](#), we reward researchers and students projects with a strong impact on society

Next to all these new activities, existing collaborations with ENLIGHT partners continued. E.g., an exhibition from the University Museum Ghent was on display in Groningen for six months in 2023-2024.

During RISE, UG staff participated in [PE Webinars](#), and participated in e.g. the ENLIGHT Impact and Teaching and Learning Conferences. Especially the Impact conference had strong links with Public Engagement. The same goes for the ENLIGHT Impact Award where a broader audience is reached with winning projects on knowledge utilization.

FUTURE

Initiatives to acknowledge and reward PE efforts of researchers are currently supported at the national level; the Dutch Royal Academy of Sciences, the Universities of the Netherlands association, the Dutch University Medical Centres Federation, and the National Research Councils NWO and ZonMW published their joint vision on this, in the policy document "[Recognition and Rewards](#)"; an approach echoed in UG's aforementioned Strategic Plan.

Based on this, the Faculty of Science and Engineering (FSE) was the first to introduce (in September 2023) a new '[Career Path](#)' for scientists, which allows professors to be also assessed on their impact (including public engagement) for promotion and tenure. This attention for public engagement is also reflected in the faculty's Strategic Plan 2021-2026, which states that 'more and more, universities are expected to have an explicit impact on society: by preparing students for their professional life, by collaborating with societal partners in research projects, and by engaging the general public in their activities'. FSE 'embraces these developments and plans to use them to its advantage'.

Based on this Strategic Plan, two actions have been undertaken:

1. Support for PE activities: an Impact officer (Oct 2023) has been appointed at Science LinX (FSE's Science Centre), to further support the development of Public Engagement.
2. Fostering Citizen Science: a tenure-track professor in Citizen Science (March 2023) at the Institute for Science Education and Communication. Since April 2023, a 5 ects course "Citizen Science" is now offered for Mater's students at the faculty, and there is an option for students to do a 30 ects research project on Citizen Science.

Central Level

From March 2023 a new position was established at the central level, for a head of Societal & Governmental Affairs at the Research & Impact Cluster.

A proposal for continuation of our Public Engagement pillar of the Open Science programme has been submitted to the Board of the University. The Public Engagement pillar will be embedded in the domain Societal & Governmental Affairs (SGA) of University Services (US). A total of 1.8 FTE is proposed for societal engagement, partly embedded in faculties, aimed at continuing the Public Engagement pillar and pillar-activities and develop the new proposed deliverables. Below are the proposed deliverables to continue and build upon the successes achieved in the first phase of the Open Science Programme.

1. *Continue of PE seed funding*

Continued organization of the successful Seed Funding pilot, for which we request an additional K€ 20 material costs yearly. Explore how to connect it to other initiatives such as the Ben Feringa Impact award and the Impact festival.

2. Extend PE training for support staff & academics.

With regard to support staff, the structural embedding of the first secretary training that was developed, is in progress. The author of the training is currently preparing the training materials and format to hand over to the pillar Public Engagements. The initial plan was for the PE pillar assistant to give the training after September 2023, on a regular basis, the Secretary network suggested to organize the training as an independent event. However, given the project financial constraints this seems unlikely at the present. A train-to-train would be an alternative; the pillar will ask one or more participants of the workshop if they could have the interest and capacity to be trainers going forward. The UG spokesperson will be included in this discussion.

With regard to the training for academics, to further formalize UG/UMCG academic training sessions on PE, we will seek to:

- Include training(s) in the Corporate Academy offer;
- Create an (E-learning) Starter package for UG new hires;
- Connect with partners and existing initiatives (e.g. including PE training in PhD-intro days, Career Perspectives, Starter package for new research staff, etc.);
- Train-to-train and peer-to-peer initiatives;
- Regular annual calendar of training - defined a year in advance on key PE topics and could be implemented with a small budget.

3. Organize events and extend PE community.

To firmly root the Public Engagement community in the UG, we will seek to:

- Coordinating implementation of the PE roadmap developed at the PE Network
- Coordinating co-creation of a PE vision, strategy and implementation plan.
- Developing a PE glossary of terms (e.g. definition of impact, public engagement, citizen science, science communication, outreach, knowledge utilization, lobbying, etc.) so that everyone speaks the same language.
- Organization of PE community events on a quarterly basis.
- Connect UG PE-Network to ENLIGHT PE-Network

4. Build central PE website and add PE within the research support portal.

Centrally managed website with a knowledge base and agenda pooling all initiatives, training and resources existing at the University.

5. *Support faculties in writing SEP societal relevance.*

The Strategy Evaluation Protocol (SEP) plays a crucial role for universities in evaluating and improving their overall societal impact. The assessment of the unit's research is done in terms of its impact, public engagement, and adoption of research findings, considering economic, social, cultural, educational, and other pertinent factors. Given the necessity for universities to align their strategies with societal needs, it becomes imperative for their faculties to effectively communicate the narrative of societal relevance within the SEP. Empowering faculties to craft a compelling narrative that demonstrates their commitment to addressing societal challenges will facilitate positive transformation and strengthen the University of Groningen's position as a significant contributor to societal progress both within the Northern Netherlands and beyond.

UG Research Intelligence Services (RISe) provides benchmarking and strategic planning support to SEP institutes for drafting SEP reports and strategic plans, both for academic impact and societal relevance. Given strong existing relationships with stakeholders, deep expertise, and the positioning of RISe in both the Research & Impact Cluster and the University Library, they should expand and roll out this service to include deep dives and narrative writing support.

A formal decision on the continuation of the PE Pillar has been delayed because of the bad financial situation of the University. Currently, the steering group on Public Engagement meets once a month, to keep the PE network going.

Also, a project team has started to prepare for an NWO call coming up to fund the establishment of a Regional Citizen Science Hub. In addition, the University of Groningen will be in the lead to elaborate the national UNL Open Science Agenda spearpoint on societal engagement and help define where Dutch knowledge institutions aim to be by 2030 when it comes to this topic. This will be coordinated by the UG PE pillar team.

University of Tartu

BEFORE RISE

Public engagement is part of the strategic plan of the University of Tartu (UT) for 2021–2025, which has an extra chapter describing the university's role as the developer of a research-based society. That includes supporting the development of a research-based worldview in society, participating in an open discussion, cooperating with the public sector in implementing studies on major challenges in society and providing evidence-based solutions to develop state policy areas.

In terms of communication, the public engagement activities with institutional support were mainly focused on one-way communication to attract potential students, popularise science and disseminate the results of research projects. Our main gates for public engagement are the university's museums with their exhibitions and educational programmes.

In terms of creating an impact in society and solving big challenges of the future, we have made great efforts to improve the entrepreneurial skills of our students and researchers to encourage them to bring their research results to society through the start-up sector. Our Centre for Entrepreneurship and Innovation has created several programmes ([From Science to Business](#), [entrepreneurial courses for students](#)) and activities for that purpose.

In the internal communication of UT, the years 2020–2021 were a time of changes. During this period, we reformed the university's communication network (around 50 people) to agree on the communication workflow and division of responsibilities between the university's different units. Previously, the expectations towards a communication specialist were very different, and it was unclear what should be solved at the institute level and what should be solved at the university level. So, we could say that our communication system at the university has been restructured during this time, creating a solid foundation for improving our communication activities, including public engagement, in the future.

Some projects stood out from the others during that period, for example:

- A few years ago, for a few semesters, our School of Law ran a project in which students offered legal assistance to the citizens of Tartu, advising them on legal matters in their everyday problems.
- In 2020, our School of Economics and Business Administration launched a pilot version of a web platform, [Futulab](#), aiming to bring project-based internships and internship opportunities from the public and private sectors or NGOs to students. In these projects, students from several disciplines work as a team, guided and supported by university lecturers or, in case of an external project idea, someone from outside. The student receives 6 ECTS credits for completing the project internship, and

the supervisor from academia has a workload of 4 ECTS for supervising one project team (3–10 students). However, due to COVID, the platform needed a more extended warm-up period to gain momentum.

- We also had some citizen science projects conducted by our researchers in the field of ecology. One of the most noteworthy was '[Looking for Cowslips](#)', which brought together thousands of people to collect information about cowslips and provide insight into the well-being of this grassland plant and related species.
- The university's Natural History Museum and Botanical Garden have organised a [nature festival](#) for years to encourage people to take part in citizen science projects and observe nature.
- When the first wave of the COVID pandemic was over and the first vaccines became available, the university launched a public campaign to help people overcome their fears about vaccination. We ran a social media campaign to receive and answer questions about vaccination and COVID. The project aimed to encourage people to get vaccinated and to help reduce fears in society. Our Communication Unit later helped disseminate the questions and answers collected during the campaign, and we also worked with the Estonian central government to help improve their information materials.

DURING RISE

As mentioned above, the network of communication specialists was reformed just before the start of the RISE project. The project has been an excellent opportunity to broaden our knowledge and learn from international experiences in public engagement. The webinars organised by the RISE team have provided a good knowledge base and network for improving public engagement formats and developing the skills of the university communication network.

As the general discussions at the international and national level have recently focused more on supporting the UN sustainability goals, combating climate change and implementing the European Green Deal at the national level in EU member states, this has also been reflected at the university level. Therefore, extra efforts have been made at UT in the last two years to improve interdisciplinary cooperation at the university. One of the results was the establishment of the interdisciplinary [Centre for Sustainable Development](#). On the one hand, it is a platform for interdisciplinary academic discussions to improve cooperation between different research fields at UT to help solve societal challenges from an interdisciplinary perspective. On the other hand, it is a platform for improving cooperation with the public sector and enriching the public debate on sustainability issues.

At the same time, the University of Tartu Library has been running a project to develop citizen science and public engagement. The two-year project, [LibOCS](#), aims to strengthen the link between science and society through citizen science in the Baltic region. The results of the project could provide a good insight into the overall situation in the field in the Baltic Sea region and what kind of institutional changes might be needed to move forward. It will also provide a basic toolkit for future citizen science projects.

The aforementioned Futulab platform has started to function as a good channel for bringing together internship opportunities and projects from the public and private sectors, as well as students and their university supervisors. Although most of the projects listed on the platform come from the private sector, some are also dedicated to solving the problems raised by the public sector and civil society. The list of almost 60 projects completed by now is biased towards the private sector because their projects are of greater interest to students from a future career development point of view. To promote the involvement of civil society, it would be necessary to carry out additional explanatory work, both among the non-profit organisations and among the students, to open up the wider impact of their cooperation.

To motivate researchers to make greater efforts in research communication and public engagement, UT gives special awards to recognise research groups that have made an impact on society with their research (Contribution to Society Award). The award was established in 2021 and is awarded once a year.

FUTURE

As outlined above, activities to strengthen public engagement at the university are developing in small steps and are often project-based. However, it is encouraging that we have a variety of them, and they combine different forms of public engagement. We also have institutional support for many of them, and reaching out to society with research results is recognised by the university and society in general. To improve in the future, it is essential to develop further the skills and tools needed for public engagement.

In 2024, the university is starting to co-create the new strategic plan that will guide the university's development over the next five years. This is a good opportunity to take a broader view of the university's goal of developing a research-based society. As the process is still in the planning stage, it is too early to say what changes will be made or how they will be implemented.

Our experience with the Futulab platform combined with the knowledge gained from the RISE project has given us food for thought on how to implement the platform better to

improve links with different research disciplines and civil society. The platform managers are also considering making the platform more inclusive for our international students, who may currently struggle with the language barrier.

We will continue with public engagement training for the university's communication network and for (young) researchers who have been very open to learning more about reaching out to society with their research results and involving society in research.

Uppsala University

The mission of Uppsala University is to gain and disseminate knowledge for the benefit of humankind and for a better world. The University seeks to contribute to open and knowledge-based public debate with freedom of expression and human rights at its heart.

The ultimate goal is for research and education to make a difference in society in the long term. Our University will put all its breadth and combined strength into supporting sustainable development, engaging with the wider community and promoting openness and respect. Uppsala University is a meeting place for knowledge, culture and critical dialogue.

Internationalisation is considered a driver for quality and enhancement of skills development. Staff and students will be given the opportunity to acquire intercultural skills to improve their potential to develop and compete in a global perspective. Collaboration with both public and private actors abroad will be intensified to further the usefulness of education and research in a global perspective. ([Mission, goals and strategies - Uppsala University \(uu.se\)](#)). Following the university's mission and strategy many structures and activities are in place and contribute to public engagement.

BEFORE RISE

Before RISE, we had a broad portfolio of engagement activity across the university. Besides the university's strategy, collaboration with society and public engagement actions are prioritized by both the municipality of Uppsala and the Region of Gotland who are ENLIGHT associated partners. This is the case for all local authorities and regions in Sweden.

DURING RISE

During RISE and the pilot phase of ENLIGHT we arranged regional academies and European Dialogues to identify and delineate societal challenges that can be addressed in our education and research activities. RISE and the WP6 has allowed us to compare ourselves internationally and learn a lot from each other, and now want to continue to support our research community in public engagement (PE). We need to foster a research impact culture where co-creation of knowledge by our researchers and society is encouraged and can contribute to the transformative potential of research and education. Our researchers need to be supported to not only communicate their research but engage with the society and co-create knowledge together with the society and through stakeholder engagement.

FUTURE

Since in the new phase of ENLIGHT (ENLIGHT 2.0), Regional Academy events are focusing on specific challenges and may not have specific activities focusing on public engagement, there is a need for developing a model/method suitable for ENLIGHT to inspire, facilitate and conduct public engagement activities to enrich the challenge-based education and amplify challenge-based R&I actions.

On the other hand, ENLIGHT 2.0 creates a new possibility for knowledge creation in each of the six challenge domains by establishing interdisciplinary ENLIGHT Thematic Networks (ETN). An ETN is a community of multidisciplinary academic teams from at least three ENLIGHT Universities joining forces around a specific topic in research and education with societal relevance and impact. ETNs will be expected to activate co-creative communities of students, teachers, researchers and variety of external stakeholders to work together on innovative solutions. The ETNs will be supported by staff from each participating university who will help academics to extend collaboration opportunities and connections. This highlights the need for a common method for supporting innovative ideas regarding public engagement. These support staff need to be equipped with methods and tools to enable them to support academics to connect and engage with external stakeholders and fully grasp and assess the impact generated by HE institutions.

For Uppsala university, the ENLIGHT alliance is an opportunity to continue sharing best practices on missions as essential as public engagement activities. The main question now is how to enhance staff and students' skills to strengthen the ongoing dialogue with society, to better consider public policies and citizens' needs for research on societal challenges. RISE and the ENLIGHT network created the possibility for us to identify a need for a more focused peer learning and staff training regarding the support and methods we are using for initiating public engagement actions. While we are creating Domain Expert Networks of the expertise from RISE, Uppsala has suggested to conduct a workshop for the collaboration experts in form of a Staff Week so that through peer learning and staff training they will acquire an international perspective enabling them to support the ETNs to promote the development of new initiatives for co-creation of knowledge between science, research and society.

Towards establishing a sustainable PE infrastructure for ENLIGHT, UU in collaboration with other partners in ENLIGHT Network suggests a workshop focusing on identifying and developing a common method for supporting PE initiatives with an international perspective. And if possible, testing such a method together with ETNs in future. This can be organised together with the experts in WP5 of RISE and can contribute to the continuity idea of the ENLIGHT RISE activities after the project ends.